

Effect of High Pressure on structural and vibrational stability of Co and Li doped ZnO ($\text{Zn}_{0.90}\text{Co}_{0.05}\text{Li}_{0.05}\text{O}$) nanoparticles

R. Thiagarajan^{a,b,*}, V. Pazhanivelu^c, S. Mohanraj^b

^a Center for High Pressure Science and Technology Advanced Research (HPSTAR), Shanghai 201203, P.R.China

^b PG and Research Department of Physics, Andavan Arts and Science College (Autonomous), Tiruchirappalli 620005

^c Centre for Research and Development, Mahendra Educational institution, Mallasamudram, 637503

In this paper, we report the pressure effect on synchrotron XRD and Raman measurements of $\text{Zn}_{0.90}\text{Co}_{0.05}\text{Li}_{0.05}\text{O}$ nanoparticles to understand its structural and vibrational stabilities under high pressure (HP) at room temperature. The selected samples were prepared using a co-precipitation method, and the quality of nanocrystalline phases were confirmed by a Bruker D2 phaser XRD diffractometer, Surface morphology of the prepared nanoparticles were carried out using a SEM [1]. The HP XRD was performed up to 28 GPa, and PV phase diagram was obtained with Third order BM EoS. The structural phase transition from hexagonal Wurtzite to cubic rocksalt structure is observed with the critical pressure range of 11.12 to 16.64 GPa, and the bulk moduli are 178 and 255 GPa^{-1} for these phases respectively. In this range, a mixed phase of both structures was observed. This same phenomenon has been observed in high pressure Raman measurements. Comparing with the lit., the critical phase transition pressure of ZnO (9 GPa) [2] is enhanced to (11.12 GPa) by Li and Co doping. So, the substitution of these elements at the Zn site tend to occupy the interstitial sites rather than substitution sites, and acted as donors instead. Hence, the doping elements lead to *p*-type conductivity with an increase in the Zn-O bond distance. But, HP compresses the crystallite size, which leads to increasing the lattice strain and reducing the band gap of this semiconductor material. As a result of lattice strain hindrance up on compression, the larger ions rather than the smaller ions try to counteract the high pressure, due to ionic force repulsion within the lattice [3]. This study provides an efficient way to modify these types of semiconductor materials for technological applications.

Keywords: High Pressure, Synchrotron XRD, Raman modes, Structural Transition

References:

- [1] V. Pazhanivelu, A. Paul Blessington Selvadurai, R. Murugaraj, Mater. Lett. 151 (2015) 112
- [2] J.A. Sans, A. Segura, F.J. Manjon, B. Mari, A. Munoz, and M.J. Herrera-Cabrera, Microelectron. J. 36 (2006) 928
- [3] J.N. Wickham, A.B. Herhold, and A.P. Alivisatos, Phys. Rev. Lett. 84 (2000) 923